

Residual Stress Study for Sustainable Structural Integrity Assessment

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Synopsis

Marine structures are susceptible to failure mechanism due to presence of both external and internal loads. A submarine is manufactured with several circular hull sections welded together and forming an entire hull. A hull section consists of several bowed metal sheets welded together and strengthened by T-section rings which are welded at repeated spaces. T-section rings are fabricated using numerous web and flange plates and curved correctly by plastically bending before welding. Fatigue life of a submarine hull is dependent on load produced from hull contraction due to surrounding hydrostatic pressure, as well as residual stress present without any applied load. Numerical simulation can be used to calculate stresses generated from hydrostatic pressure. However, predicting residual stresses resulting from bending and welding processes can be more involved. Moreover, the predicted stresses need to be validated by measurement.

Incremental centre-hole drilling (iCHD) is broadly applied technique to measure residual stress. The iCHD technique however is limited to near surface measurement which can contribute to misleading structural integrity assessment. On the other hand an over-conservative estimate of stress due to

welding process can lead to reduced life estimate. It is thus imperative to analyse residual stresses accurately and deep into metal parts in order to move away from decade old conservative estimates. This paper reviews various techniques available for analysing residual stress field and considers multiple techniques with an aim to provide an optimum solution.

Keywords: Residual stress, measurement, finite element analysis, sustainable structural integrity

1. Introduction

Residual stresses can be generated in engineering parts in different means. Thermal treatments to impart useful properties is a regular means of inducing residual stress. Additional manipulation of parts, e.g. fabricating final shapes may cause non-linear and random redistribution of residual stress, thereby giving rise to significant distortions.

A submarine hull essentially comprises T-frames and rolled plates welded together. Bending residual stresses can easily be calculated. Stresses within T-butt welds are significantly tensile in and around the weld and can critically affect crack growth mechanism. The combined effect of bending and welding residual stresses results in a “Z shape” through thickness residual stress distribution, with

Fig. 1 Classification of residual stress measurement method

tensile component at inner surface and compressive at outer surface of the hull.

Several techniques (Withers and Bhadeshia 2001) are available ranging from non-invasive to totally destructive, summarized in Fig. 1. Non-invasive methods include magnetic, ultrasonic and diffraction. Semi-invasive methods include deep-hole drilling (DHD) and incremental centre-hole drilling (ICHD). Invasive methods, where components are completely destroyed include Sachs (Sachs 1927, Garcia-Granada et al. 2000), layer removal and contour (Withers and Bhadeshia 2001, Treuting and Read 1951) methods. The methods are also classified by their penetration, i.e. length scale. While X-ray diffraction (XRD) and ICHD techniques measure near surface residual stress, DHD and neutron diffraction (ND) measure residual stresses some 'cm' into engineering parts.

2. Residual Stress Measurement Techniques

2.1 Non-Invasive Techniques

Non-invasive methods to measure residual stress distribution are briefly reviewed.

2.1.1 X-Ray Diffraction

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) is a frequently applied non-invasive technique to obtain near-surface residual stress utilising material inter-atomic spacing. X-rays have wavelengths (\AA) in the order of a typical inter-atomic spacing. X-rays scattered from polycrystalline material can constructively interfere to produce diffracted beam. The angles corresponding to maximum diffraction intensities are used to obtain inter-planar spacing, d , of diffraction planes through Bragg's law. By using stress-free sample the reference spacing, d_0 can be obtained. The elastic strain is obtained through:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{d - d_0}{d_0}$$

In the absence of reference sample, differential technique ($\sin^2 \psi$) can be used to determine the diffraction angle 2θ and hence lattice spacing d

for multiple inclination angles ψ of the specimen surface obtaining the stress measurement.

2.1.2 Neutron Diffraction

Neutron diffraction non-invasively provides residual stress field in polycrystalline specimen by measuring strain components from the changes in lattice spacing when neutron beam is incident on the specimen. If 2θ is the intersection angle of incident with diffracted beam then a constructive interference with consequent intensity peak occurs satisfying Bragg's law

$$2d^{hkl} \sin\theta = \lambda$$

where d^{hkl} is interplanar spacing between Miller indices (hkl). Fitzpatrick and Lodini (2003) provides more detail of the method.

A stress-free lattice spacing d_0^{hkl} is required to measure absolute values of residual elastic strain defined by diffracted and incident beam:

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{d_i^{hkl} - d_0^{hkl}}{d_0^{hkl}} = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda} - \cot\theta\Delta\theta$$

For a reactor source where wavelength remains same, $\Delta\lambda = 0$ and $\varepsilon_i = -\cot\theta\Delta\theta$. In pulsed beam measurement tools, $\Delta\theta = 0$ and $\varepsilon_i = \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda} = \frac{\Delta t}{t}$. Residual stresses are obtained using the measured strain components through Hooke's law.

$$\sigma_{xx} = \frac{E}{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)} \left[(1 - \nu)\varepsilon_{xx} + \nu(\varepsilon_{yy} + \varepsilon_{zz}) \right]$$

where E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson ratio. Similar equations hold for yy and zz components.

2.1.3 Ultrasound Technique

Ultrasonic waves are commonly utilized to detect flaws in engineering materials, i.e. structural health monitoring. However, they can also measure applied and residual stresses (Schneider 1997). The Ultrasonic method is the only portable technique that can non-destructively provide through-thickness stress measurements in broad selection of materials.

The method exploits acoustoelastic property of materials by measuring the velocity of ultrasonic waves travelling through a component. An increase in velocity indicates the presence of compressive stress and conversely a decrease indicates tensile stress. Near-surface stresses can be measured using critically refracted longitudinal waves with the

ultrasound transmitters and receivers being attached to acrylic wedges. Through-thickness stresses are measured using both longitudinal and shear ultrasonic waves with transmission or reflection probe systems.

The technique is best suited to measure relative changes in stress within a material, however with careful and accurate calibration the relative measurements can be transformed into absolute values, accounting for temperature and microstructure variations.

Ultrasound waves travel through a component at different speed which depends on stress, temperature and microstructure of specimen. The change in time-of-flight Δt of ultrasound waves traveling through a sample is related through:

$$\Delta t = \Delta t_{AS} + \Delta t_{RS} + \Delta t_T + \Delta t_M$$

where Δt_{AS} is change in time-of-flight due to change in applied stress, Δt_{RS} is change in time-of-flight caused by change in residual stress, Δt_T is temperature change related change in time-of-flight and Δt_M is microstructure change related change in time-of-flight.

Microstructural changes affect acoustoelastic coefficient, L_{ij} , of a material, which is used in final calculation of applied/residual stress:

$$\Delta\sigma = (E \cdot \Delta t) / (L_{ij} \cdot t_0)$$

where $\Delta\sigma$ is the stress change, E is elastic modulus and t_0 stress-free time-of-flight.

2.2. Semi-Invasive Techniques

The semi-destructive techniques are mechanical strain relief methods and maintain the integrity of engineering components for further application and is therefore a practical measurement technique.

2.2.1 Incremental Centre-Hole Drilling

The incremental centre-hole drilling (ICHD) utilises surface strains measured when a hole is drilled through the centre of a strain gauge rosette, Fig. 2a. The hole is drilled to pre-set increments where relaxed strains are measured. Through numerically determined compliance functions these measured strains are transformed into stresses, TN-503-5 1993. Integral method (Schajer 1998) is used to obtain residual stress distribution from relaxed strains. The strain relaxed on the surface along generic x-direction, at hole depth h , is related to residual stresses by

Fig. 2 Schematic of semi-invasive methods

$$\varepsilon_x(h) = \frac{1}{2E} \int \{ (1 + \nu) \hat{A}(h, H) [\sigma_x(H) + \sigma_y(H)] + \hat{B}(h, H) [\sigma_x(H) - \sigma_y(H)] \} dH$$

where $\sigma_x(H)$ and $\sigma_y(H)$ are residual stress distributions along the generic orthogonal x and y directions; \hat{A} and \hat{B} are numerically determined influence functions of an inverse problem where unknown stress distributions $\sigma_x(H)$ and $\sigma_y(H)$ are determined numerically by dividing maximum hole depth into N intervals and approximating the stresses in each interval using suitable stress distributions.

2.2.2 Ring Coring

In ring core (RC) method residual stress in a component is measured by machining an annular groove into the component and measuring subsequent relaxation of surface strain within the central core at set depths using strain gauge rosette, Fig. 2b, Civin and Vlk, 2009. Using influence coefficients which are numerically determined using finite element analysis (FEA) the surface strain relief is decomposed into residual stress distributions at each increment.

Bi-axial residual stresses including σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and σ_{xy} are averaged over central core cross-section. The measured incremental strain can be used to

provide either single set of bi-axial stresses averaged over the machined depth or a depth variation in bi-axial residual stresses.

2.2.3 Deep-Hole Drilling

Deep-hole drilling (DHD) technique determines through-thickness residual stress distribution by measuring change in diameter of an initial reference hole as a result of circumferential trepanning of a core of material containing the hole (Smith et al. 2000). Steps in DHD method (Fig. 2c, Kingston et al. 2006) includes: (1) gun-drill of a reference hole, (2) accurate measurement of initial reference hole diameter at several (N) angles, at a number of depth increments, giving $d(\theta, z)$, (3) trepanning a core of material containing reference hole free from rest of component using electric discharge machine, (4) re-measuring hole diameter after core removal, giving $d'(\theta, z)$.

Normalised distortions $u_{rr} = \frac{d'-d}{d}$ (loosely termed as diametral strains) relate to residual stress $\sigma_{xx}(z)$, $\sigma_{yy}(z)$ and $\sigma_{xy}(z)$ in the plane perpendicular to reference hole axis. Deformations at a hole in a finite-thickness planar infinite plate are related to remote planar stress components assumed constant through the plate thickness through elasticity. Least squares analysis is used to evaluate unknown stress components from measured normalised reference hole distortions:

$$\{\sigma(z_i)\} = -E(M^T M)^{-1} M^T u_{rr}$$

Where,

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + 2\cos 2\theta & 1 - 2\cos 2\theta & -4\sin 2\theta \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 + 2\cos 2\theta_N & 1 - 2\cos 2\theta_N & -4\sin 2\theta_N \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig. 3 Three rolls bending

3. Typical Residual Stress Distribution in Submarine Hull Sections

During manufacturing of submarine hull structure, metal sheet plates are rolled using three rolls bending procedure followed by welding. The points in Fig. 3 represent the contact points with the three rolls. Maximum curvature is at point B and the required curvature occurs at point C. The bending residual stress can be calculated analytically.

An approximate analytic solution to obtain circumferential residual stress due to three rolls bending is explained by Aguiar et al. (2001) and Queener and Angelis (1968). The solution uses constitutive elastic-plastic bending, bending moment and elastic spring-back relations to evaluate residual stress, see Fig. 4. Longitudinal residual stress within rolled sheet following unloading step can be obtained by adding elastic stress due to unloading at each 'y' position of the sheet from stresses already present.

Assessment procedures, e.g. R6 or BS7910 provide estimates of welding residual stress predicting highly tensile hoop stress (using yield value) at weld toe and reducing to zero at some depth depending on heat input. However, these welding stresses are better estimated by using numerical methods such as finite element analyses and/or by measurement techniques. Typical residual stress profiles measured using DHD method in different submarine structures by Ficquet et al. 2012 is reproduced in Fig. 5. The stresses are a

Fig. 4 Bending residual stress

Fig. 5 Longitudinal (hoop) stresses in submarine structure

combination of both bending and welding stress. Also shown is the bending stress. The combined stress distributions predominantly compares well with bending stress profile.

4. Optimisation of Measurement Methods

The residual stress profiles measured by Ficquet et al. 2012 are essentially complex in nature. A simple superposition of the theoretical bending stress and welding stress estimated by assessment procedure would over-predict the stress distribution. This would subsequently affect predicted performance and life of a component. With more accurate stress analysis the prediction would improve including improvement in design and manufacture.

To preserve integrity of an engineering part it is always desired to employ non-invasive residual stress measurement techniques. Stresses measured close to the outer surface in Fig. 5 are compressive whereas stresses near inner surface are tensile. Therefore, stress analysis through the depth of the specimen is important for accurate structural integrity assessment. The neutron diffraction (ND) technique can non-destructively measure sub-surface residual stress fields. However, the technique itself is not portable and has limited sampling size, so that only part of the component or mock-up is used in the ND measurement. This would off course redistribute the original residual stress field present within the component.

For field application, the ultrasound (US) residual stress measurement technique provides a practical application. Not only the measurement is non-invasive but can also provide through-thickness distribution. The US technique coupled with XRD technique can become a useful tool in providing on-site residual stress measurement at different length scale. The XRD measuring near-surface stresses can obtain any sharp stress gradient. This combination of measurement tool is particularly suitable for the application on a submarine structure.

In the same way, the semi-invasive methods including the ICHD and the DHD can be combined to provide near-surface and sub-surface residual stress distribution. As these are semi-invasive the integrity of the component is retained.

For critical components, it is advisable to utilise as many analysis techniques as available. The use of multiple methods as demonstrated by Hossain et al. (2017) not only reduces the error in measurement but also improves confidence. A proposed residual stress advisor with multiple application of methods is demonstrated in Fig. 6. Conventionally, different measurement techniques are used to report different residual stresses analysed according to that method. In contrast, in the proposed route multiple methods are used resulting in only one accurate stress field.

Fig. 6 Typical residual stress advisor

5. Conclusion

A number of residual stress analysis techniques were reviewed. Both non-invasive and semi-invasive methods were considered. Residual stress distributions measured in typical submarine structure was reproduced from elsewhere to illustrate their complexity. Residual stress measurement methods suited to the submarine structures were discussed. A methodology on optimising the measurement for more accurate structural integrity was briefly presented.

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